

RAISING THE AWARENESS OF THE POPULATION ON THE USE OF ECO-FRUITS AS HEALTHY FOODS

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ABSTRACT

Considering the fact that organic foods are consumed in the smallest amount in our market, there is a need to raise the awareness of the population in the use of organic foods and with particular emphasis on eco-fruit. Of their number, there are some types of eco-fruits that we can encounter in the mountain areas of the Shara, and which have an extraordinary benefit to human beings. The organic fruits that grow on Sharr Mountain are in considerable numbers as their benefits positively result in one's organism. These organic fruits grow in the Sharr Mountains are organic and above all are fruits that are not injected with phytohormones, pesticides, herbicides and do not contain other poisons as well as toxins that are harmful to the organism, despite that they are rich in vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates that need an organism. Organic Fruits of Sharr Mountain grow in unpolluted environments where air is clean and does not contain harmful toxins to organisms. Organic fruit research brings innovation to the market in general and their consumption results in a vital organism.

Keywords: Healthy fruits, Organic food, Nutrition's, Sharr Mountain, Use of eco-fruits.

Introduction

Bio foods

Research and studies have shown that organic products are rich in chemical substances as vitamins (A, B complex, C, folic acid), minerals, antioxidants which are necessary for the human body. *Bio foods* are those foods that have maintained their natural components and don't have added artificial ingredients or contamination

during production. Bio food is a new concept that has not previously existed in the past because all foods were organic.[1]

The advantages of Bio foods

Respect for nature and man increases awareness and helps to reduce pollution of the environment, which is often associated with the use of ant parasitic and nitrates. Food, especially fruits and vegetables have a stronger flavor unchanged - the original. More nutritious although from this perspective, the difference with classic products is not as important. From most of recent studies shows that biological food bring a greater amount of micro nutrients, is potatoes, tomatoes, peaches, lettuce, cabbage, spinach contain slightly more vitamin C, magnesium, iron. [2]

Disadvantages

Respect for good agricultural practices has a cost that naturally weighs on selling prices of these products. Thus, bio products are 20-30% more expensive than normal products.

- ✓ Shorter time of conservation.
- ✓ Stronger taste: What is the advantage on the one hand, for some can be a disadvantage. For example, black bread made of integral flour (with all the fiber of its crude) has a flavor that everyone likes.
- ✓ Choosing organic foods should be first and foremost, a groove, with the ultimate goal respect for the environment and personal health.
- ✓ Not yet known more for ant parasitic effect, organic fertilizers or chemicals have on our body; however, by focusing attention on organic food, can be a way to prevent health problems. The main problem remains somewhat high price of these products. However, the expansion of bio market to depress prices gradually.[3]

Eco fruits

Apple

Its contents include: water, protein, very little fat, sugars such as fructose, glucose and sucrose, mineral salts, phosphorus, calcium, magnesium and vitamins E, C, B1, A.

Positive effects on human health:

- ***Fights asthma*** - an American study has shown that the abundance of vitamins and nutritional elements of apple cleanse the airways.

- **Maintains control of cholesterol** - fibers like pectin achieve lower cholesterol levels in the blood by reducing the risk of heart disease as arteriosclerosis.
- **Laxative effect** - Apple is known for its virtues laxatives if constipation.
- **It reduces the risks of cancer:** Apple reduces the risk of digestive diseases roads.
- **It reduces the dangers for kidney stones.** [4]

Pear

It is rich in fiber, vitamins A, B1, B2, E, folic acid, also in their content they also have copper, phosphorus and potassium, small amounts of calcium, iron and magnesium.

Some of the health effects that have on our body pears are:

Pears has a particular importance to heart disease as the pears are fibers that are a good opportunity to keep the heart healthy but also regulate blood pressure and regulate the level of harmful cholesterol.

Pears has a positive effect on the brain as it contains copper a mineral that helps maintain the nervous system and also promotes mental harassment, contain glucose and fructose which enable the maintenance of energy during the day. [5]

Pears due to the high concentration of fibers contained in this fruit has the ability to prevent the formation of various types of cancers because they are rich in antioxidants protect cells from free radicals and contain acids that prevent the formation of cancer.

Cherry

Cherry is a good source of fiber and vitamin C. Therefore, doctors often advise cherry dietician as super foods. [6]

Benefits from Cherry:

It helps memory. Cherries have been known for helping memory and prevent memory loss, it is noted by a component that anthocyanins found in cherries that positively affects the brain and stimulates neurotransmitters.

Cherry has soothing and enhances sleep. This is another feature of cherry, people who consume more cherries make deeper sleep compared with those who did not consume ,it happens because the cherry contains a hormone known as melatonin hormone that is known to regulate sleep cycles in the body so a peaceful sleep and pleasant recommended cherry consumption.

Treats cancer. The patient of cancer increases the chances for recovery cherry, cherry because it has nutritional properties that help in the fight against cancer and heart disease. [7]

Raspberry and Blackberry

Blackberry fruits contain sugars, vitamin C, carotene, vitamin E, organic acids, pectin etc. As well as its leaves are rich in vitamin C, organic acids, and aromatic tonic course. Fatty oil in the seeds is the extent to 12%.

Raspberry is rich in vitamins A, C, B1, B2 and B6 with organic acidic, iron, magnesium, phosphorus, calcium, manganese and sugar trees. It is rich in cellulose and helps regulate body weight.

It contains salicylic acid (the active ingredient of aspirin) that is used to alleviate pain, reduce temperature and anti-inflammation.

This fruit also positively affect vision, strengthens immunity, whereas it was concluded that prevents the emergence of cancer of the breast and cervix. [8]

Strawberries

Strawberry is a good product that enables elimination of the disease as:

Hypertension - high electrolyte content potassium made strawberry excellent solutions for those suffering from high blood pressure.

Constipation - thanks to water containing fibers and helps to smooth the stool.

Diabetes - thanks to the low glycolic index, strawberries can be enjoyed without worry of people who suffer from diabetes.

Depression - the content of folic acid makes healthy solution for strawberry brain function.

Cholesterol - daily consumption of strawberries helps in controlling and reducing the level of fats in the blood.

Heart - regular consumption reduces the risk of cardiac arrest at 32%.

Tumor diseases - strawberries contain antioxidants that neutralize carcinogenic agents and reduce inflammation. [9]

Blueberries

Numerous studies have shown that blueberries helps improve vision, clear the arteries from atherosclerosis, against anemia, strengthening of blood vessels, increased memory, inhibition of infections channels tract, in maintaining memory and physical force and in of body weight control. The American Institute for Cancer Research says that blueberries is one of the best sources of antioxidants, substances that can slow down the aging process and reduce cell damage that can lead to cancer. [10] Bilberry are dotted with vitamin C, then it is an excellent source of sugar, protein and mineral substances such as potassium, sodium, manganese, chromium, and iron.

Use of pesticides - in uncontrolled mass

Pesticides are commonly used in the process of cultivation of fruits and vegetables. Their use consists in the destruction of bacteria, mold, insects, etc., that can cause the destruction of the product. Usually pesticides are in powder or liquid form and are divided into:

Figure.1. Uncontrolled treatment of plant cultures with pesticides, insecticides, herbicides and fungicides

- Insecticides,
- Fungicide and
- Herbicide, which have a specific action on insects, bacteria, mold and worms.

It is likely to eliminate one part of the pathogenic micro flora and stimulate the growth of another pathogenic micro flora which is also a different kind of plant. [11]

Figure 2. Treatment and toxic effect of phyto hormones in various fruit and vegetable products

The effect of pesticides

Pesticides cause a large number of health problems including neurological disorders and endocrine system, congenital defects, cancer and many other disorders. Centre for Disease prevention and safety controls have yielded some results showing that a high percentage of individuals tested had a concentration of pesticides or other chemicals in urine or blood. Also data from this center was to American children between 6-11 years of age have a higher concentration of pesticides, organophosphate, which are known for their skills high neurotoxin. [12] We also need to know that the effect occurs in humans in small doses. Children are particularly vulnerable to the toxic effects of pesticides compared with the extent of their lower body, rapid development and high degree of consuming products contaminated with these chemicals. To

children who have been exposed to pesticides from residues in food can cause slow growth, endocrine system disorders, reproductive, and immune, some types of cancer and other organs injuries.

Prenatal exposure to certain pesticides can cause developmental disorders. Some studies have found that the level of pesticides in children is low or no measurable to subjects who have consumed organic food. Farmers also have a higher incidence of this disorder during intensive exposure to certain pesticides most frequently by for Agricultural spray or use of these chemicals.

Figure.3. Teratogenic effect in newborn infants from unchecked control of pesticides in plant cultures, damage to the gastrointestinal tract and pathologies associated with the newborn baby

Discussion

Story at-a-glance

A new study revealed 11 pesticides that increase your risk of Parkinson's disease even with very low-level exposure – levels lower than are currently being used. People with a certain common gene variant had a two to six times greater risk of developing Parkinson's disease when exposed to pesticides. Separate research has further revealed that ambient exposure to organophosphate pesticides also increased the risk of developing Parkinson's disease. Minimizing your exposure to pesticides – around your home, in your community, and via your diet – is an important way to lower your risk of Parkinson's. The risk of Parkinson's disease clearly increases with exposure to certain environmental toxins, such as pesticides. Pesticides, herbicides, and fungicides are potent toxicants that may cause disruptions or damage to the neurological system, including your brain. What is perhaps most concerning is that even ambient exposure to pesticides has been found to increase the risk of Parkinson's disease considerably, and this was further confirmed by new research linking the disease to extremely low-level pesticide exposure. [13]

Commonly Used Pesticides Linked to Parkinson's, Even at Low Levels

Last year, UCLA researchers linked a fungicide known as benomyl to Parkinson's disease.² The chemical was banned by the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) after it was determined to be a potential carcinogen. That study found that binomial blocks the aldehyde dehydrogenase (ALDH) enzyme. When working properly, ALDH changes aldehydes, which are toxic to dopamine cells, into less toxic compounds. When ALDH is blocked, however, this transformation does not occur, contributing to the development of Parkinson's. For the most recent study, the researchers revealed 11 pesticides in all that inhibit ALDH and increase the risk of Parkinson's disease. The effects were seen even with very low-level exposure – levels lower than are currently being used in everyday applications. The study's lead author said: *"We were very surprised that so many pesticides inhibited ALDH and at quite low concentrations, concentrations that were way below what were needed for the pesticides to do their job. These pesticides are pretty ubiquitous, and can be found on our food supply and are used in parks and golf courses and in pest control inside buildings and homes. So this significantly broadens the number of people at risk."*

Conclusion

Your health is under siege from every direction. Environmental toxins, ultra-processed foods, EMFs, government-subsidized GMOs and a host of other threats surround us. It is simply not possible to protect yourself unless you are armed with cutting edge health information. The most complex tasks can be made easy if you just take one step at a time. Taken as a whole, this 30-tip plan makes for a comprehensive guide that can change your life. Just a few of the topics addressed are:

- What to eat and when to eat it
- Exercise strategies that you can implement today
- The power of emotional health
- Enhancing your health with essentials like air, sunshine and water
- How to get the restorative sleep that your body requires

It may seem that health and wellness are no longer the norm. An upload epidemic sweeps the country, the obesity rate is skyrocketing, life expectancy is dropping and chronic diseases are rampant. Our communities are being damaged at every level and the only way to reverse these trends is through education and personal example. My 30-tip plan provides you with the tools you need to take control of your health. The time is ripe for revolution — a health revolution.

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